

THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING TEXT ANALYSIS IN THE LESSONS OF "READING LITERACY"

Utanbaeva Dildora Abdikhadirovna

Trainee-teacher of the Department of Pedagogy of Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute.

Sodiqboyeva Azizaxon Saminjon qizi

Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute

Correspondence course "Primary Education" 2st stage student.

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Abstract. This article covers the content of primary education mother tongue literacy and reading literacy lessons to teach students to read and understand the text and analyze it. The importance of foiling from innovative techniques such as the method of working on poetic texts, the method of grammar syntactic, the method of growing informative approaches is also stated when working on the text.

Keywords: primary class, native language, text, text analysis, text comprehension, reading process, poetic text, lexical units, informative approach.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ МЕТОДОВ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНАЛИЗУ ТЕКСТА НА УРОКАХ "ГРАМОТНОСТЬ ЧТЕНИЯ"

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается содержание обучения учащихся чтению и пониманию текста и его анализу на уроках начальной образовательной грамотности и грамотности чтения. Также в работе над текстом отмечается значимость использования таких инновационных методов, как метод работы над поэтическими текстами, грамматико-синтаксический метод, метод культивирования информативных подходов.

Ключевые слова: начальный класс, родной язык, текст, анализ текста, понимание текста, процесс чтения, поэтический текст, лексические единицы, информативный подход.

Developing reading and text comprehension skills in primary school students is a pedagogical process aimed at 4th grade students (correct, fast, expressive and understanding reading) as well as awareness of reading rules, choosing a work, getting used to reading books and consistently organizing actions along the way, enjoying reading a work, understanding the content of the work and ensuring that the skills It's about either. Qayumkhojayeva commented: "the culture of Reading and reading forms in students such skills as reading a book, analyzing it

and expressing their thoughts about this work during their educational activities. The culture of reading also represents the maturity of the reader in this field. The culture of reading is an educational and educational phenomenon characteristic of all mankind during the developed era of tamadduns. It also represents the skills, interests, creative opportunities that are generated in the student as a result of Education”[3;7].

“At the beginning, middle and end of the reading process, the student uses a complex of primary knowledge and skills in language skills, cognitive and metacognitive strategies, and content formation”[2;5]. In the course of reading, elementary students rely on acquired linguistic sath units, educational-cognitive, cognitive skills.

It is important to understand the reading of the text by readers, the use of many innovative techniques and modern technologies to understand it. A.Lenhart, K.Purcell, A.Smith, K.A study by the zickuhrs shows that “today, students are using technology to study both at home and at school and for leisure purposes” [6].

Method of working with poetic text. Elementary students are interested in reading a poem, saying it. As part of this process, the text of the poem “in the lesson of the mother tongue” was selected to expand their knowledge of them poetically, to cultivate the framework of artistic analysis. Each reader is given the text of the poem and given time to read it. After that, they will be asked to answer the following assignments. In the process of working with the content of Halima Ahmedova's poem” in the mother tongue lesson (from the series “textbooks to my son(“)” in the 4th grade textbook” reading literacy”[8;10], the following tasks can be used:

Task 1. Speak the content of the poem in your own language.

Task 2. Why do we say “mother tongue”, not “father tongue”?

Task 3. Who taught you to speak?

Task 4. Verbally state what you understand when it comes to honoring your “native language”by looking at the picture.

Assignments provide the basis for the development of such qualities as skills for elementary students to conduct activities independently and a sense of responsibility, agility, initiative, broad worldview.

Grammatical syntactic method. Taking information on the grammar of the Uzbek language and the syntactic branch of linguistics with regard to age, the skills of correct sentence construction are taken into account.

Stage 1.	Lexical meaning of the words on the topic selection of sets of lexical units
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Stage 2.	Attaching 3-4-5 words to one sentence.
Stage 3.	Drawing up 5 sentences that contain content related to the title
Stage 4.	Starting the text from the paragraph. Unduli use of entries
Stage 5.	Creating text based on sentences with meaning and meaning

Method of growing informative approaches. In this, students must read the information given in the text expressively and verbally divide the idea expressed in it into two groups and speak it.

“Grandpa Kulal

A person who has not one, but several trades in life is happy. In ancient times, it turned out that those who knew the craft of pottery were very revered. Because although it turns out that the dishes at that time are not as rich as they are now.

The old man, Rahim bobo, became famous in pottery. The jugs they made, the trays, the florets, put on, every item turned out to be so beautiful and unobtrusive, convenient to use.

In fact, it will be difficult to master the craft, to cope with its difficulties.

To make a ceramic object, first the soil is taken and the clay is snowed. Then the form is given. There will be a special countertop for this. Grandpa Rahim complex performs this work with diligence and endurance in quality. Grandfather Rahim taught many of his students their craft.

They say:” unar from the craft”[4].

It is clear that working on text analysis in readers, analyzing the content and essence of the text in one whole and proportionally, realizing information, information from texts will become the basis for the development of communicative - speech competencies in them. Therefore, to achieve the effectiveness of this process, it is necessary to ensure the appropriate structure of topics in educational textbooks, as well as to have a high level of methodological, lexical supply, to approach the contextual approach with the system.

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